

Advancing National Security: Greece's Strategic Plan for Next-Gen MILSATCOM Systems

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Abstract

This article proposes a plan for the development of the Greek satellite system (GR-MILSATCOM). The benefits of such a project would be significant for strengthening national (and international) Defence, Security and Economy. Such a system will also be a catalyst for the Hellenic Air Force (HAF) in transitioning to the new space era, enhancing its operational capabilities and the resilience of its communications. Greece currently seeks to acquire its own satellite system, primarily for military and governmental communications. Greece aims to design, develop, launch, and operate a telecommunications satellite equipped with advanced technologies and strong encryption, operating in a geostationary orbit (GEO). This satellite will provide continuous wide-area coverage and connectivity to the national Armed Forces (and governmental entities) in various operational theaters¹. While existing national telecommunications infrastructures are capable, they have inherent limitations that hinder nations from operating with maximum efficiency and security. A modern SATCOM system can enhance existing national military communication networks, ensuring fast, reliable, and secure data transmission during military operations. Additionally, it can provide the desired nations' autonomy in the field of SATCOM while contributing to technological superiority and economic growth.

Keywords

Military Satellite Communications, MILSATCOM, Governmental Satellite Communications, GOVSATCOM, Secure SATCOM, Space Security and Defence, Hellenic Air Force, HAF

1. Introduction

In the modern era, information is one of the most decisive factors for national Security and Defence. Satellite Communications (SATCOM) play a central role in the defence strategies of nations, offering resilient and reliable exchange of information, in a rapidly changing geopolitical environment. Their utilisation is critical for the effective conduct of military operations and the safeguarding of national security. The strategic importance of SATCOM in national Defence is very high, offering significant capabilities for Command, Control, Communication, Computer and Intelligence (C4I).

Space is an enabler not only for the digital transformation. The Space industry is rapidly evolving as we enter a new era, including SATCOM. Agile New Space players are embracing new trends in the space technology in order to develop services benefiting diverse users in both public and private sectors². By following a comprehensive roadmap for leveraging these technologies, nations can not only enhance their defence capabilities but also maintain strategic superiority in the increasingly digitised and interconnected realm of global Security.

Secure SATCOM are essential for the resilience and strategic autonomy of the nations, both in Space and on the ground. They provide the basis for security - and safety - of critical missions and operations, including crisis management, land and border surveillance, and protection of the key infrastructure³.

Space has long been an important domain for military operations and has been used actively by NATO for its own SATCOM programme for almost 55 years. However, it was not until 2019 that NATO Allies formally

recognised Space as an operational domain, opening the door to a greater focus on how Space can play a pivotal role in Defence⁴.

A little later, in 2022, after the Russian invasion in Ukraine, the European Union (EU) leaders also identified Space as a strategic domain through the “EU Strategic Compass”⁵ and called for an EU Space Strategy for Security and Defence. Building on this political momentum, the Commission and the High Representative have developed the first-ever “EU Space Strategy for Security and Defence, 2023”⁶. As highlighted in this Strategy, the gap between Space and Defence should be bridged, while flagship programs in Space for Security and Defense purposes must be prioritized.

The EU needs independent, secure, resilient, and high-speed space-based connectivity to satisfy the needs of EU institutions, bodies, agencies and Member States. Secure SATCOM provide one or two-way reliable, accessible and guaranteed satellite service for communications. To connect European Governments, the EU is working on both the deployment of GOVSATCOM, a component already part of the “EU Space Regulation, 2021”⁷, and the deployment of the IRIS², the new “EU Secure Connectivity Programme”^{3,8}, to be operational by 2030.

In this context, the development of a national military telecommunications satellite (MILSATCOM) is a strategic imperative to enhance a nation’s defence capabilities and secure communications infrastructure. It is also an opportunity to advance technological capabilities, and enhance research and innovation in space sector. The technological advancements made during the system’s development could also lead to numerous spin-off technologies that benefit civilian sectors, by Enhanced (and Secure) Communication Networks.

The primary purpose of establishing a national MILSATCOM system in Space is to provide a secure, resilient and high-capacity communication network tailored specifically for military use. This satellite will ensure fast, seamless and real-time communication across all branches of the Armed Forces, enhancing coordination, operational efficiency and decision-making capabilities.

2. Strategic Impact of National MILSATCOM Systems

2.1 Contribution to National Security

The development and deployment of a MILSATCOM system will ensure national autonomy in safety and Security. The utilization and development of space infrastructure contribute to achieving autonomous capabilities to respond to national Security needs.

The system will also provide a dedicated, secure and resilient communication infrastructure for defence operations. It will serve as a critical component in ensuring that military forces can maintain superiority in all operational environments. The forecasted improved communication capabilities will provide a tactical advantage, facilitating real-time data sharing and decision-making.

The critical role of SATCOM in several key areas is underscored by NATO:

Secure and Reliable Communications across vast distances

This capability is vital for coordinating operations, especially in remote or hostile environments where traditional communication infrastructure is lacking. NATO's recent investment of €1 billion in SATCOM services over 15 years highlights the importance placed on these capabilities⁹.

Support for Command and Control (C2)

SATCOM are fundamental for transmitting orders, intelligence, and real-time data between Command Centers and deployed forces, ensuring synchronized and efficient mission execution. NATO's

SATCOM infrastructure supports operations at all levels (strategic, operational and tactical), providing access to mission-critical information¹⁰.

Intelligence Gathering and Surveillance

SATCOM support Intelligence, Surveillance and Reconnaissance (ISR) operations by transmitting data from various sensors and platforms to analysis centers. This capability enhances Situational Awareness and decision-making processes, critical to national Security⁹.

Resilience and Redundancy

In times of crisis, terrestrial communication networks may be vulnerable to disruption. SATCOM provide an alternative communication pathway, ensuring continuity of operations even when ground-based systems are compromised. NATO's strategic rivals have been conducting space operations that threaten the security of the Alliance, highlighting the need for resilient space-based infrastructure⁴.

Integration of Allied Forces

SATCOM enable different nations' forces to operate cohesively, during multinational operations. NATO's reliance on member states to provide space capabilities, such as SATCOM, underscores the collaborative nature of these operations¹¹.

2.2 Economic Benefits

The development of a new MILSATCOM system is expected to create jobs and drive economic expansion through technological advancement and manufacturing. Apart from that, any excess telecommunications capacity can be leased to Allies, such as national/governmental organisations, or to private telecommunication companies, contributing to the rapid amortisation of the project. The Greek RFI, published in 2024, also incorporated this option¹.

Moreover, in the field of narrowband communications for the tactical domain, there has been a rapidly increasing structural shortage of satellite capability worldwide in recent years. This issue requires intensive international coordination and cooperation. By investing proactively, nations and organizations such as NATO, could have tactical satellite capability over extended areas, be well-prepared to fulfill their international role in this domain, and be able to further build this capacity¹². These requirements could potentially be addressed by EU systems like GOVSATCOM and IRIS², which aim to provide secure and resilient satellite communications for EU citizens and governmental users. However, their ability to fully cover the increasing demand for tactical narrowband SATCOM—especially for highly mobile, real-time battlefield communications—remains uncertain.

SATCOM capabilities of the defence sector may be supplemented by commercial contracts as required. With the huge growth in the commercial supply of high-quality SATCOM capability, it is becoming opportune to explore dual-use scenarios in collaboration with industry: deploying commercial SATCOM infrastructure for military applications. Through limited co-investment, defence sector could have this commercial capability made suitable for military deployment, and also strengthen the business case for industry¹².

2.3 Operational Support for Forces Deployment

Some of the EU member states have deployed forces in external theatres over the last decades as part of national or international missions or operations (such as under NATO, or the EU). Those missions and

operations involve the use of satellite communications either based on proprietary governmental satellites or third-party assets (such as systems managed by private commercial operators) ^{3,5}.

3. Evolving Landscape of Secure SATCOM: Drivers, Challenges and Future Trends

3.1 Factors driving the demand for secure SATCOM

The need for secure SATCOM was first presented in 2004 with the EU Council’s decision “European Space Policy: ESDP and Space” ¹³ and again in 2016 with the “EU Global Strategy” ¹⁴. However, the Russian invasion highlighted the necessity to address this issue more effectively. The 2022 EU Strategic Compass is the last key driver for future demand. It is estimated to lead to new investments, modernisation of forces and new operations.

At the same time, an increase in the data transmission requirement for essentially all of the terminals used by military forces is anticipated.

The sensitivity to new and/or increasing threats (i.e. contested operations, jamming, cyber security, etc.) is also estimated to result in a demand for more “secure” capabilities compared to traditional commercial SATCOM solutions³.

Furthermore, the locations of future threats, crises and operations is difficult to anticipate, as exemplified by the war in Ukraine in 2022. As such, the ability to rapidly adapt, with an increasing level of flexibility and mobility is estimated to represent an important driver. The trend towards an increasing number of units equipped with a communication on the move capability is estimated to increase³.

3.2 Current Challenges in SATCOM

In today’s military applications supported by SATCOM, security, resilience, information assurance, and link efficiency technologies are inextricably linked. Military operations are becoming more complex as conflict areas grow more dispersed on a global scale, with a growing need to support a diversity of on-the-move, on-the-pause and fixed platforms. At the same time, security threats are becoming more apparent, raising concerns that nations, terrorist groups, criminals and individual hackers can jam, interrupt and endanger military operations. The challenge is to meet, in a secure and guaranteed way, the increased demand for raw capacity generated by continuous growth in space data rate requirements for military purposes¹⁵.

Existing SATCOM systems, while robust, face several critical challenges that limit their effectiveness in supporting modern military and national security operations. Primary challenges include:

- ✓ Bandwidth limitations
- ✓ Cyber Security vulnerabilities
- ✓ Coverage gaps
- ✓ Latency issues
- ✓ Aging infrastructure
- ✓ Capacity constraints

3.3 Technological Drivers transforming the Secure Satellite-based Connectivity

Several structural drivers have started to transform and largely increase the volume of capacity offered through satellite assets. These will likely also impact the capacity and services available for secure

connectivity. Overall, digital technologies are at the heart of this transformation alongside the use of higher frequency bands and other features.

Ultimately, the technological benefits will likely go in three directions³:

- ✓ An increase in the volume of available capacity
- ✓ A higher flexibility in the ability to dynamically allocate the capacity and design of services
- ✓ A higher cost efficiency of satellite assets

3.4 Latest Trends in SATCOM

The SATCOM domain is undergoing unprecedented development across the board. Technical developments in satellites, terminals and ground infrastructure are moving at lightning speed.

New innovative launch capability providers, such as Space-X, are making satellite launches increasingly common. Today, we see huge investments in commercial constellations of satellites, mainly in Low Earth Orbit (LEO). Examples include Starlink and OneWeb. Because of the short distance between the satellite and Earth, these constellations provide connections that can compete with land-based fiber networks in terms of latency and bandwidth¹².

Beyond the prominent rise of LEO constellations, there is a growing trend toward deploying satellite constellations across various and multiple orbits, not just the traditional single satellites in GEO orbit. In GEO, innovations such as micro-GEO satellites are also emerging. Additionally, the adoption of multi-band and high-frequency bands is becoming more widespread, enhancing the flexibility and capacity of SATCOM systems.

High Throughput Satellites (HTS), software-defined satellites, and satellites equipped with on-board Artificial Intelligence (AI) and edge computing capabilities, are also key trends that are revolutionizing SATCOM. Moreover, Direct-to-Device (D2D) technology is addressing connectivity challenges in underserved regions, offering a practical solution for extending communication networks.

Meanwhile, there is evidence that state actors are increasingly focusing on developing SATCOM specific attacks. These attacks are also being developed across the spectrum: ranging from attacks in the electromagnetic domain (such as jamming, directed energy deposition and interception) to kinetic attacks and cyber-attacks on ground-based infrastructure, including management infrastructure. Technical, geopolitical and commercial developments in the SATCOM domain require a broad (re)orientation of Defence's need for more secure and robust high-capacity SATCOM links¹². Recent advancements in quantum and laser communications, along with blockchain technology, are showing great promise in providing robust protection against the above security threats.

4. The GR-MILSATCOM System and its Impact on the Hellenic Air Force

4.1 The GR-MILSATCOM system

Greece is pursuing the development of a single satellite in GEO, capable of providing autonomous and secure satellite communications. The satellite should also be positioned to lease any excess capacity, which is a key element for recouping the overall project costs. Another important aspect is the Greece's intention to offer these services to allied nations and/or organisations, which will create funding requirements from those entities¹.

Since the exact budget, project timeline, and specific intentions regarding collaborations with other countries and organizations remain still unknown, only a general idea for developing such a system can be

outlined. If the initial mission parameters (requirements and orbit) are not altered along the way, the recommended approach is to opt for deploying 2x Micro-GEO satellites, with a different timeline for each of them. Initially, Greece should procure a Micro-GEO satellite, which will be small and cost-effective, allowing for rapid deployment and the provision of desired services.

Although much smaller than GEO satellites, micro-GEO satellites are being placed in the geostationary orbit and already provide (successfully) satellite communications. Their advantages - such as lower weight and size, simpler construction, reduced costs, easier and quicker deployment, and streamlined licensing from regulatory authorities - make them increasingly popular. They are an ideal choice for countries with smaller budgets that still wish to develop their own MILSATCOM and/or GOVSATCOM systems. It is worth noting that Micro-GEO satellites (as well as laser communication satellites) do not require approval from the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) for GEO deployments.

The leasing of excess capacity from the Greece’s first satellite could support the financing of the second one. This option offers the redundancy and uninterrupted operation required for a MILSATCOM system. A realistic estimate for the first deployment would be a budget of under €60 million, and a timeline of approximately two years. This satellite could use high military frequency bands, such as X or MIL-Ka band, and is projected to have a lifespan of 10 to 15 years in geostationary orbit.

The second Micro-GEO satellite could further improve connectivity between existing national or European satellite constellations in lower orbits by utilizing laser Inter-Satellite Links (ISLs). Additionally, it could be equipped with a Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) payload to further enhance security. This approach aligns with Greece’s recent efforts to integrate into the EuroQCI framework. As a reminder, the country is already taking steps to participate in this broader EU initiative, which the country’s Ministry of Digital Governance (GR-MoDG) signed on 3 December 2019¹⁶.

Greece’s focus has been primarily on developing the terrestrial infrastructure for the EuroQCI, with three Optical Ground Stations (OGS) selected in collaboration with the European Space Agency (ESA):

Figure 1: Greece’s terrestrial infrastructure for the EuroQCI, Source: HELLAS QCI¹⁷

The National Infrastructures for Research and Technology (GRNET), operating under the auspices of the GR-MoDG, is at the moment, the coordinator for the HellasQCI project¹⁸.

Additionally, the world's first commercial OGS has been established in Greece, by the Norwegian-based company K-SAT, with plans to integrate it into a multi-mission network operation¹⁹. This K-SAT telescope could potentially establish optical links with the proposed GR-MILSATCOM system. Furthermore, optical telescopes designed for laser communication with the system could be deployed on military ships within Greece's territorial waters and/or on Greek islands, providing additional redundancy to the overall system.

Here is an illustration of the proposed integration of the GR-MILSATCOM system into the existing GreeCom²⁰ network:

Figure 2. The Proposed Integration of the GR-MILSATCOM System into the existing GreeCom Network,
Source: C. Giannopapa, A. Staveris-Polykalas and S. Metallinos²¹

A hybrid approach (1x Micro-GEO satellite + 1x GEO satellite) should also be considered, particularly given the extensive space heritage of “traditional” military GEO communication satellites. Additionally, part of the revenue generated from leasing the capacity of the first satellite could be allocated towards funding the larger (and more expensive) GEO satellite. This strategy could play a pivotal role in ensuring the overall economic feasibility of the project.

To further reduce the overall project costs, Greek governmental authorities could first wait to evaluate the performance of the initial satellite. If they are sufficiently satisfied with its results, they could then deploy another similar Micro-GEO satellite, rather than investing in a more expensive and slower-to-establish Full Operational Capability (FOC), GEO satellite. In any case, while the first Micro-GEO satellite is being developed and deployed, efforts to acquire the second satellite should be initiated concurrently.

Throughout all phases of the project, comprehensive cost assessments must be conducted, and funding sources should be secured in a timely manner. Additionally, technological trends (e.g., D2D connectivity or laser SATCOM) and challenges surrounding MILSATCOM systems (particularly cyber-security threats) should be continually reassessed. Adhering to the project timeline is another critical success factor for the mission.

At the same time, engaging with allied countries that have similar systems could yield benefits by helping to avoid mistakes and missteps. Greece can draw insights from the examples set by other pioneering

countries and organisations that have successfully developed state-of-the-art communication satellites. In those cases, at least two GEO satellites were typically developed, with investments amounting to several hundred million euros.

Building on this approach, Greece should also pursue a system with interconnectivity capabilities, both with its national LEO micro-satellite network and with European SATCOM networks such as IRIS², EU GOVSATCOM or EUQCI. Regardless of which option Greece ultimately chooses, it is crucial to focus on the timeline, budget and funding, collaboration with stakeholders, partnerships with allied countries and/or organisations, risk assessment, and compliance with international regulations.

4.2 Contribution to the Hellenic Air Force (HAF)

Communications are a fundamental factor both for the effective C2 of Air Forces and for the successful conduct of operations. Military communication systems must be interoperable with the communication systems of other branches of the Armed Forces, as well as with other governmental, Allied, and civilian communication and information systems. Secure, continuous, resilient and real-time connectivity between Air Units and assets enables the dissemination of operational information, enhances shared Situational Awareness at all levels of warfare, and consequently contributes to the flexible and effective use of Air Power²².

Network-Centric Warfare (NCW) and Interoperability

The HAF is shifting towards a NCW environment, where seamless interconnection of military units (aircraft, Command Centers, surface and ground forces) is critical. A MILSATCOM system will enable:

- ✓ Real-time ISR data transmission
- ✓ Integration of information across all branches of the Armed Forces
- ✓ Superior Situational Awareness and battlefield coordination
- ✓ Autonomous and seamless interoperability with Allied Forces

Support for Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) and C2 Systems

UAVs have acquired significant payload capabilities (weapons, optical sensors, radars, etc.), leading to their increasing use in modern warfare and their integration into the military arsenals of most countries²². With the rapid advancement of UAVs, the HAF will require SATCOM for:

- ✓ Remote control of UAVs over long distances
- ✓ “From sensor to shooter” capability, to locate, acquire, and strike targets with pinpoint accuracy
- ✓ Transmission of high-resolution video, images and data in real time to Operations Centers
- ✓ Better integration of UAVs with manned aircraft in a Common Operational Environment

Hostile missiles or drones interception

The MILSATCOM system will enhance the HAF's ability to intercept enemy ballistic missiles or drones by providing real-time data and intelligence through systems like the Shared Early Warning (SEW) satellite system.

Support Air Lift Operations

Airlift operations are vital to the success of joint operations, as they enable the airborne transport, deployment, sustainment and recovery of personnel, assets and equipment. At the same time, airlift provides fast and flexible options for military, national and international organizations, allowing them to respond effectively to crises at a local, regional or global level²². A MILSATCOM system will play a crucial role

in supporting airlift operations by ensuring secure, real-time connectivity between Command Centers and airborne assets, enhancing coordination and mission effectiveness in complex operational environments.

Secure and Resilient Communications

The system will provide resilient, secure and encrypted communications, essential for modern Air Force operations. In the event of conflict or cyber attacks, communications relying on commercial networks are vulnerable, whereas a MILSATCOM system ensures exclusive use and control.

Autonomous Strategic SATCOM

A national MILSATCOM system will provide autonomy, reduce dependence on third parties, and strengthen national strategic planning for the Armed Forces, including the HAF.

5. Conclusion

The development of the GR-MILSATCOM system marks a significant strategic advancement in national Security, technological innovation and economic growth. By establishing a secure, resilient, and autonomous SATCOM system, Greece will enhance its defence capabilities while reducing dependence on third-party infrastructures. The proposed Micro-GEO satellite system ensures cost-effectiveness, rapid deployment, and potential revenue through leasing excess capacity. This initiative not only aligns with broader European security frameworks but also strengthens the country's position within NATO and EU defence collaborations.

Acquiring such a system will also mark the HAF's transition to the new Air and Space Force era, enabling it to operate in a modern, interoperable and NCW environment, ensuring operational superiority and resilient communications against current and future challenges.

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Short Biography:

Lieutenant Colonel Fotios Giantsis graduated from the Hellenic Air Force Academy in 2002. He served for several years at the 117 Combat Wing as a pilot on F-4E AUP fighter aircraft. He has been a flight instructor and test pilot, having accumulated nearly 2,500 flight hours. He was assigned to NATO as an Air Operations Expert at NRDC-GR HQ and later commanded the Operational Support Squadron of the 113 Combat Wing. He is a graduate of the Hellenic Supreme Joint Defense College and the Hellenic Air Force War College. He holds a Master's degree (MSc) in *Space Technologies, Applications & Services* from the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA). His training also includes certifications in *Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning* and *Cyber-security* from various universities. He has authored several scientific studies on Space Technologies, and has actively participated in numerous workshops, conferences, and forums on Defence, Space and High Technologies.